

Why white noise is not enough?

On using radio front-end models while designing 6G PHY

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Existing models and optimization goals

RX signal power: $\alpha P d^{-\gamma}$

Noise power: N

$$SNR = \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{N}$$

+ frequency-selective fading

- Typical aim: Spectral Efficiency Maximization (increasing bandwidth or transmitted power)

$$C \left[\frac{\text{bit}}{\text{s}} \right] = B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{N} \right)$$

New aim (exist in 5G): Energy Efficiency

RX signal power: $\alpha P d^{-\gamma}$

Noise power: N

$$SNR = \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{N}$$

+ frequency-selective fading

$$EE = \frac{B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{N} \right)}{f(P) + P_{CONST}}$$

- PERFECT assumption: $f(P) = P$ and $P_{CONST} = 0$ and no wanted signal distortion

Power amplifier considerations

RX signal power: $\alpha P d^{-\gamma}$

Noise power: N

$$SNR = \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{g(P) + N}$$

+ frequency-selective fading

$$EE = \frac{B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{g(P) + N} \right)}{f(P) + P_{CONST}}$$

Nonlinear behaviour of Power Amplifier: degrees of freedom

Cross-layer design for 6G

➤ Multiple nonlinear elements in a transceiver, e.g.,

- Power Amplifier
- ADC
- Battery (rate-capacity effect)

➤ 6G needs to consider these models:

more degrees of freedom

vs

higher complexity

Example 1: PA operating point adjustment

- State of the art solution: set operating point to obtain proper Error Vector Magnitude and Spectral Emission Mask (at TX)
- Soft-limiter, class B PA, OFDM waveform, 2 battery types

Example 2: Non-gaussian signal optimization

- Lower number of subcarriers = lower envelope fluctuations = possibly lower nonlinear distortion power
- Use case: IoT applications (devices using 1-2 subcarriers in the uplink)

Example 3: Massive MIMO

- Common belief: as number of antennas (K) increases the SNR rises

$$SNR = \frac{\alpha K P d^{-\gamma}}{g(P) + N}$$

- In reality: in many channels distortion is directed as wanted signal

$$SNR = \frac{\alpha K P d^{-\gamma}}{K g(P) + N} \approx \frac{\alpha P d^{-\gamma}}{g(P) + N}$$

Two-path channel, $K = 128$, IBO = 3 dB, Signals:
— Desired — Distortion

Example 3: Massive MIMO

- E.g., no gain for LoS channel with number of antennas (K)
- Need for proper algorithms, e.g., nonlinearity minimizing precoding or nonlinearity-aware precoders (shown for OFDM: lower BER possible than in no-nonlinearity case)

Example 4: ML for front-end aware network optimization

- Exact models of each front-end are typically not known
- Additional processing stages (e.g., scheduling, traffic steering etc.) cause the global model is too complex
- Machine Learning tools (like Reinforced Learning) suitable for, e.g., finding optimal operating point for Massive MIMO Base Station

Thank You (Dziękuję) Questions?

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